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ROUTES TO ALL-BENZENE POLY[n]CATENANES VIA BREAKABLE DIRECTIVE IMIDE BONDS

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Possible ways to high molecular weight poly[n]catenanes, which can be built from wide range of different blocks (including all-hydrocarbon) via selectively breakable directive imide bonds in main chain are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Space of mechanically interlocked molecules (MIMs) is separate and novel area of Chemical Space. Topological bond allow to combine incompatible before properties of materials, so synthesis of mechanically interlocked polymers open new horizons for industry and progress in general [Ref.1]. Poly[n]catenanes are object of chemical competition still. A record-breaking poly[n]catenane was synthesized by Qiong Wu et al. in Rowan Group [Ref.2]. However, modern methods have some limitations on the synthesis of nonpolar MIMs, which very interest, because of their unique properties. The most applicable technique in this case is covalent directing bonds, that was proved by Schill [Ref.3], Godt [Ref.4] and Itami & Segawa [Ref.5]. But high degrees of polymerization and high molecular weight were not achieved yet. Because of it, further searching of effective strategies retain their relevance as before and discussions continue.

DISCUSSION

General conception (idealized) shown in Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3:

1. Face-to-face orientation of rigid-rod side chains (from rigid-rod main chain) with their mutual bonding and then destruction of main chain (Figure 1).

Figure 1.

2. Rigidity provides linearity and limitations of molecular mobility (axial rotations with minimal swings) - i.e. desired direction (Figure 1 and Figure 2).

Figure 2.

- Ideal nodal (directive) bond must be rigid-rod, planar, atropisomeric, easy to forming, selectively destructible (Figure 2).
- Rotational energy barriers of Free Rotation Segments must be minimal [Ref.6], to facilitate face-to-face bonding of side chains (Figure 3).

a) rotational energy barrier ~ 16 kcal/mol
 b) rotational energy barrier ~ 2 kcal/mol

Figure 3.

- Polyrotaxanes can be realized analogically (Figure 4)

Figure 4.

Cyclic imide bond chosen as directive bond in example of rot, which demonstrate side chains bonding to nodal monomer at first, then main chain forming and homocoupling of side chains between themselves in last. The alternate way is main chain forming at first, then bonding to main chain of side chains and then

coupling of side chains between themselves, but this way encounter with solubility problems of rigid-rod polyimides (main chain), possibility of imide cycles opening (with distortion of linearity) and side reactions of palladium species with imides [Ref.7]

Homocoupling of side chains can be replaced by cross-coupling. Cross-coupling is more preferable because of combinatorial decreasing of INTERmolecular bonding of side chains (between side chains of different main chains), but homocoupling is more faster in INTRAmolecular bonding of side chains (of same main chain) because of combinatorial reasons too. Main chain is polyimide in fact. Side chains are polyphenylenes in fact. Rigidity and linearity of polyimides and polyphenylenes provides desired direction of side chains. Because of it, for improving solubility of chains into them must be introduced relevant side groups. Imide bonds of main chains must stay stable in coupling reactions of side chains. Rings of formed poly[n]catenane are complected from side chains, so after closing of rings (via coupling of side chains between themselves) polyimide main chain must be destroy selectively (rings must stay stable). Remaining polar groups remove by reductive deamination. For improving solubility of final all-benzene poly[n]catenanes, rigid rod oligoimides and chlorinated organic co-solvents (ODCB, EDC etc.) can be used [Ref.8]. Side chains can include 6-membered heterocycles and/or internal alkynes (with or without terminal alkynes for homocoupling or cross-coupling of side chains between themselves).

For minimization of possible side reactions (because of high reactivity of palladium species) was chosen appropriate order of steps. At first, from aniline **1** via Fu-Dai-Littke protocol [Ref.9] obtain boronic acid **3**. Commercially available aryl halide **4** reduce selectively with HSiCl₃ and DIPEA [Ref.10] to aniline **5**, for coupling with boronic acid **3** via Fu-Dai-Littke protocol. Formed diamine **6** have two unactivated chlorines with some sterical hindrance. Suzuki cross-coupling in this case must be improved by appropriate ligands and conditions. Buchwald protocol with SPhos ligand can be chosen [Ref.11] with some excess of oligomeric boronic acid **7** [Ref. 19]. Length of oligomer **7** is very important moment. This is side chain and rings of formed poly[n]catenane are complected from side chains. Mutual bonding of face-to-face oriented side chains possible when distance between their cups are minimal. From geometrical point of view, we need to form equilateral triangle. Because of it, length of oligomer **7** must be approximately (because of molecular scissoring) equal to distance between nodal monomers of main chain, which adducted with face-to-face oriented side chains (see Figure 1). Oligomer **7** can be formed in step-growth Suzuki cross-coupling of benzene-1,4-diboronic acid and substituted dibromobenzene (by 3,3-dimethyl-1-butene to 1,4-dibromo-2-iodobenzene addition in Heck reaction) for solubility improving (branched alkyls are suitable too). After addition of oligomer **7** to diamine **6** we can capping side chains with m-diiodobenzene **8**. Next step requires differentiated functionalization of amino groups. In next steps toluene can be used as co-solvent. Knolker-Braxmeier route to isocyanates [Ref.12] is applicable in this case. Sterically hindered amine will transform to isocyanate and other amine stay protected by Boc-groups in structure **10**. Isocyanates imidization with **11**

[Ref.13] will result with terminal protected diamine **12** in final. For trapping of t-BuOH excess (side product) we can use 1,4-phenylene diisocyanate.

Previously prepared structure **13** (from benzidine and dianhydride) is segment of free rotation. Axial turns will encounter functionalized caps (as aryl iodides) of neighboring (on same main chain) face-to-face oriented side chains to each other (A+B in Figure 1). Boc-removing can be carried out thermally [Ref.14] or via HCl addition with further imidization with acetic anhydride [Ref.15]. Resulted main chain polyimide **14** have idealized geometry, which shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5.

Intramolecular connection of corresponding side chains between themselves (green + red in Figure 5) realized in this example via palladium/TBAF catalyzed aryl iodides homocoupling with high dilution in DMF, to prevent intermolecular side chains homocoupling [Ref.16]. More preferable variant of this protocol is Pd(OAc)₂/PPh₃ (1/2); TBAF; DMF. Because Pd(PPh₃)_n species failed (See Scheme 3 in [Ref.25]) in decarbonylative opening of imide cycles [Ref.7]. For yields improving we can add NEt(iPr)₂ as in similar Hassan et al. protocol of aryl halides homocoupling [Ref.22]. Toluene is suitable as co-solvent in this step [Ref.23]. Palladium catalysts with phosphine ligands are compatible with cyclic imides in general [Ref.24].

At this step can take place palladium decarbonylative insertion into imide cycles, but it's not distort main chain linearity critically. Decarbonylative insertion decreasing in six-membered imide cycles versus five-membered [Ref.7]. Resulted structure **15** is pseudo poly[n]catenane until main chain will be destroyed. Hydrazinolysis (in toluene/aniline blend as solvent) via ammonium salt-accelerated method [Ref.17] seems most preferable. Remaining amino groups must be removed. With help of convenient reductive deamination protocol [Ref.18], for example. All-benzene (alkenylated) poly[n]catenane **17** is final aim.

Figure 6.

Main chain linearity can be stabilize (after reductive elimination of inserted into imide cycle palladium) via trans-symmetrical steric hindrance for palladium insertion into imide cycle (see Figure 6). Substitution can be realized via cycle opening of halogenated anhydride/Suzuki cross-coupling with t-Bu-substitued boronic acid/closing of anhydride cycle [Ref.20].

[For preventing photochemical activity of rylene segments all reactions must carry out in darkness.][Ref.21]

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